

Chapter 4. Overcoming the challenges of achieving transformative change towards a sustainable world

Supplementary materials

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Annex 4.1. Identifying challenges

The five overarching challenges were identified through a five-step process that included expert opinion and evidence gathering with different forms of literature reviews. The process adapted existing expert elicitation methods - like the IDEA protocol ('Investigate', 'Discuss', 'Estimate', 'Aggregate') of Hemming et al. (2018) - and adhered to the process protocols of IPBES about transparency and confidentiality. To establish this process, literature on expert consultations was reviewed (Baker et al., 2019; Hemming et al., 2018). There is limited application and reflection of expert elicitation use in interdisciplinary research and even less in public policy making (Morgan, 2014). As a result, there are few established models for elicitation that met the requirements under this task. Instead, the approach described below was developed.

Step 1 - Identify and discuss

As Morgan (2014, p. 7176) notes, "to conduct an expert elicitation, there must be experts whose knowledge can support informed judgment and prediction about the issues of interest". Coordinating lead authors and lead authors of chapter 4 as selected experts started by asking the question: what are the systemic, foundational challenges to transformative change? The first round of expert inputs was realized in May 2022 in the First Authors Meeting, held in Montpellier. All the working sessions focused on debating the different identified 'blockages' to transformative change and arrived at five broadly defined challenges.

Adapting the IDEA protocol phases "Identify" and "discuss" proposed by Hemming et al. (2018), the first step adapted the 'discussion' phase. Specifically, because the questions about the challenges and barriers to transformative change had already been identified in a broader sense in the IPBES transformative change assessment's scoping document and in the initial author meeting in May 2022, there was little purpose in ensuring the anonymity of participants using these initial documents and discussions, the coordinating lead authors identified a conceptual entry point to the core question presented above.

- Focus on challenges to transformative change for biodiversity restoration and conservation that are systemic and foundational, meaning that the way they will manifest in different contexts and their scales of operation and influence will vary. As such, the aim was to bring to the surface the deeply entrenched, the "root causes" of what blocks transformative change.
- Focusing on challenges to any type of transformative change was not the goal. The focus is on change related to biodiversity, nature, ecosystems and environmental issues.
- Challenges to transformation are interconnected and the character of their interconnections differs in different contexts. As thus, providing a universally representation of these relations is not possible and not a desirable outcome of the assessment.
- The epistemological and ontological principle of pluralism in searching and synthesizing literatures across disciplines is a guiding principle, without assuming the validity or efficacy of one discipline over the other. Different scholarly bodies will be reviewed for finding evidence and for weaving in explanations and knowledge about the identified challenges.

The second phase of the IDEA protocol, 'Discuss' was realized first in group discussions in person in Montpellier and in follow-up, deeper discussion groups that were formulated around the identified challenges.

Step 2 - First literature review

Five working groups with three to five experts (each a mix of lead authors and coordinating lead authors) were formulated and conducted literature reviews based on their interdisciplinary expertise and knowledge backgrounds. The objective of this step was to explore the significance and recognition of the identified challenges in the cross-disciplinary literature that addresses these challenges. This first round of literature reviews narrowed the broad challenges initially identified to more specific dimensions. The reviews conducted in this phase informed the First Order Draft of the chapter reviewed in January 2023.

Step 3 - Second systematic and scoping literature reviews

Focusing on the narrowed-down challenges, working groups conducted literature reviews to deepen and broaden the evidence upon which to build the assessment. Six working groups were formulated: five dealt with the challenges, and one working group looked for cross-over literature that identified ways to overcome the challenges. In this stage, contributing authors with complementary disciplinary backgrounds were invited to join the different working groups and assist in the literature reviews. This explanation is to clarify the starting points of the data management reports that are cited and included in the chapter. In this stage of the literature review, the working groups met weekly to discuss the screened literature, excluded papers and selected papers were discussed. Additional literature searches were coordinated at the working group level as well as at the chapter level. In this stage of the literature review, the working groups met between one to one and half hours to discuss findings, mis-conceptualizations, knowledge gaps as well as connections between the challenges. All meetings of the chapter 4 team have been recorded through minutes and PowerPoint slides to ensure that the conceptual and methodological lessons learnt are documented.

The different literature reviews are documented in detail in the data management reports¹²³⁴⁵.

Step 4 – Synthesis

The synthesis of the different findings and reflection on limitations of current scholarly work was realized first during the assessment second author meeting that was held in May 2023 in Costa Rica. The team of coordinating lead authors and lead authors worked in structured sessions to deepen the synthesis of each challenge, create a better synthesis of challenges to transformative change across the challenges, and identify cross-chapter findings for the proposed ways of overcoming the challenges. Coordinating lead authors and lead authors worked in structured sessions to deepen the synthesis in each challenge, create a better synthesis of challenges to transformative change across the challenges and identify cross-chapter findings for the proposed ways of overcoming the challenges. The chapter team worked in responding to the received over 500 review comments from the first external review, the co-chairs of the assessment and the IPBES Multidisciplinary Expert Panel. Working to respond to these review comments further deepening the analysis as the author team reviewed additional records recommended by external reviewers and the IPBES Multidisciplinary Expert Panel. This work confirmed the challenges, and their framing

¹ Review of literature on the persistent and pervasive relations of domination forged in colonial eras (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10250609>)

² Review of literature on power imbalances and inequalities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251325>)

³ Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252250>)

⁴ Review of literature on unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252304>)

⁵ Review of literature on limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251408>)

developed by the author team. As presented in the Second Order Draft of the chapter, this step resulted in additional conceptualizations and findings:

- The reviewed literature offers significant evidence that the identified challenges are underlying a variety of barriers and that there are manifestations of these challenges at local, regional, State levels of governance.
- These challenges do not, at this point, necessarily point to solutions. They emerged at a different historical time and have become entrenched parts of how humans live in the world today. Therefore, it was decided to focus on characterizing the challenges to identify opportunities to address them in the present and going forward.
- There is anecdotal evidence of the interconnection of the challenges and how they reinforce each other but there is limited literature on how this is evidenced and documented at local levels, that limits the synthesis at this stage to present an overarching model of how these challenges relate across scales.
- The majority of these challenges are recognized by Indigenous Peoples and local communities as also reported by many IPBES dialogues.

Step 5 - Zooming out and complementary evidence through case studies

In this step, specific questions were formulated - repeating the step 'Identify' from the IDEA protocol - to guide the identification of case studies. Step 5 was conducted in parallel with step 4 and was initiated during the Second Author Meeting in 2023 in Costa Rica. The team decided to identify case studies with the following criteria:

- Case studies need to provide evidence on how every challenge manifest and/or is experienced. If the case study can also provide evidence of interrelations of the challenges, this evidence needs to be backed with more than one reference.
- Case studies need to cover three habitats: Oceans, Land/Terrestrial Ecosystems and Urban.
- Case studies that illustrate ways of overcoming the challenges especially employing nature-based solutions were also identified in response to external reviewers' comments that were received from the first external review (January-March 2023)
- Case studies need to be supported from a synthesis of published literature across different authors/sources.

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Annex 4.2. Linking challenges with the IPBES transformative change assessment scoping report

The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 4 should address a wide range of challenges and obstacles that impede transformative change toward a sustainable world for nature and people, with a focus on strategies to overcome them in order to advance global, regional and local visions for a sustainable world for nature and people. The chapter provides evidence on political, social and economic inequalities, among and within countries.

Table SM.4.1. Interpretations of challenges and the ways they manifest from a pluralistic perspective.

Challenges relating to:	Identified Challenge	Ways challenges manifest from a pluralistic perspective: (relating to the Scoping Document of the IPBES transformative change assessment).	Record of the conducted literature reviews
Ways of seeing, thinking and knowing (Views)	Persistent and pervasive relations of domination, especially those that emerged and were propagated in colonial eras (section 4.2.1)	Worldviews, mindsets, mental models, systems of values and perceptions often refer to or capture ways of seeing and thinking. Ways of thinking manifest in the values and aspirations voiced and captured in visions, thereby trapping the imagination of other possible worldviews. Ways of seeing and thinking further manifest in how people perceive reality or a situation, including how they conceptualize transformative change, what constrains practices to achieve it and how to deal with cultural systems.	Data management report: Review of literature on colonial modernity ⁶ .

⁶ Review of literature on the persistent and pervasive relations of domination forged in colonial eras (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10250609>)

<p>Ways of organizing, regulating and governing (Structures)</p>	<p>Economic and political inequalities (section 4.2.2)</p>	<p>How power is exercised and where it resides plays a paramount role in how transformative change is propelled or blocked. The interdependencies within and across individuals and systems and relations of systems overall are manifestations of ways of organizing, regulating, and governing. are manifestations of ways of organizing, ins and path-dependencies are created and enforced, how entrenched institutions are reinforced, and how power influences ways of relating.</p>	<p>Data management report: Review of literature on power imbalances and inequalities⁷.</p>
<p>Ways of organizing, regulating and governing (Structures)</p>	<p>Inadequate policies and unfit institutions (section 4.2.3)</p>	<p>Formal and informal institutions, broadly including political, legal, technological, physical (e.g., infrastructure), economic/financial and other social systems regulate and propagate the dominant ways of organizing services, transactions and relations conceptualized as structures. Challenges relate to ways of organizing, regulating and governing manifest through personal, sociocultural and systemic inertia (e.g., market systems, rules), lock-in effects and path-dependencies, policy inertia and the lack of transformative governance approaches that are</p>	<p>Data management report: Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies⁸.</p>

⁷ Review of literature on power imbalances and inequalities (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251325>)

⁸ Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252250>)

		integrative, inclusive, informed and adaptive.	
Ways of doing, behaving and relating (Practices)	Unsustainable consumption and production patterns and practices (section 4.2.4)	Seeing behaviours and actions at individual and collective levels as challenges to transformative change, examining how they gain salience and how socio-economic profiles and contexts further propel unsustainable (and extractive) production and consumption patterns. These behaviours are manifestations of the challenge and include unsustainable habits, lack of appropriate action or inaction, insufficient responsiveness to information, what is often understood as salience and entrenchment of informal institutions.	Data management report: Review of literature on unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices ⁹ .
Ways of knowing (Structures and practices)	Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems (section 4.2.5)	Knowledge systems, including the production, ownership, advancement and sharing of diverse forms of knowledge and evidence play a role in enforcing structures and shaping practices for transformative change. Such systems include and are not limited to science-policy-community interfaces and ways that Indigenous and local knowledge is accounted for and appreciated for transformative change. Knowledge systems are not apolitical; aspects of power over knowledge	Data management report: Review of literature on limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems ¹⁰ .

⁹ Review of literature on unsustainable consumption and production patterns and individual habits and practices (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252304>)

¹⁰ Review of literature on limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10251408>)

production processes and policy processes as well as their access and institutionalization interrelate with systemic inequalities and fuels biodiversity loss. This challenge manifests, amongst others, as lack of trust in science for policy making (e.g., failures of research to inform or guide policy) and in de-appreciation or neglect of forms of knowledge that question the status quo.

Table SM.4.2. Interpretations of challenges and the ways they manifest in barriers.
Barriers are highlighted in cursive letter.

CHALLENGES RELATING TO	IDENTIFIED CHALLENGE	WAYS CHALLENGES MANIFEST (BARRIERS)
Ways of seeing and thinking 	Prevailing worldview based on persistent relations of domination, particularly those that emerged and were propagated in colonial eras (Section 4.2.1)	Worldviews form the way we see the natural and social world, and how we portray the relations with people and nature. Persistent relations of domination between people and nature manifest in how categories are drawn (<i>categorize and rank</i>), and how complex socio-ecological dynamics are understood through <i>measurement, simplification and regimes of management</i> . (Ways of) Thinking that people and nature are separated, manifest also through perceiving nature as a commodity <i>justifying resource concentration</i> .
Ways of organising, regulating, governing 	Economic and political inequalities (Section 4.2.2)	Ways of organising and regulating economic and political power can generate impermeable barriers to transformative change. <i>Concentrated wealth and power shapes policy</i> as it leads to disproportionate representation of interests in policy formulation. Across national and global levels, <i>international monetary system constraints policy autonomy</i> that is necessary to advance transformative change. Economic and political inequalities are entangled. Such inequalities further manifest through decisions about investments are made according to <i>shareholder interests and profit rather than the public interest</i> including biodiversity restoration.
Ways of organising, regulating, governing 	Inadequate policies and unfit institutions (Section 4.2.3)	Ways of organising and regulating can generate barriers to transformative change when complexity and the dynamics of social-ecological systems are not accounted for, and magnitude and urgency of biodiversity loss are inadequately addressed with the structures in place. This challenge can be recognised in policy (ways of regulating) and in institutional structures backgrounding policy responses. A barrier is the lack of <i>accountability in biodiversity policies</i> , and the weakening of environmental state because of <i>the neoliberal (re)structuring of State policies</i> (including liberalisation and austerity). There is a variety of reformist responses to biodiversity loss that create a fallacy of action while legitimising underlying drivers of biodiversity loss, stalling transformative change. Not accounting for the complexity and dynamics of socio-ecological systems, <i>institutional structures are unfit</i> (socially, temporarily, functionally) creating oversights for dealing with biodiversity loss and, as a result, limit the effectiveness of biodiversity-focused policies.
Ways of doing, behaving, relating 	Unsustainable consumption and production patterns and practices (Section 4.2.4)	Ways of doing and behaving in day-to-day life often result in unsustainable production and consumption patterns. A <i>GDP-centric economic growth model</i> underpins these patterns globally; the trends vary widely between and within regions though owing to <i>socioeconomic differences</i> . Such disparities are reinforced by <i>telecouplings</i> that influence ways of relating to these issues (e.g., separating people from their impacts). Finally, <i>ingrained habits and conformist practices</i> promote the persistence of these trends. Indeed, one of the most significant barriers to transformative change lies in the hold that habits and institutions have over social life.
Ways of knowing 	Limited access to clean technologies and uncoordinated knowledge and innovation systems (Section 4.2.5)	Knowledge systems are not apolitical; aspects of power over and access to knowledge production processes, including their institutionalisation, are informed by and draw on systemic inequalities, obstructing the development of transformative visions and practices that might address biodiversity loss. This includes the intentional or unintentional <i>marginalization of indigenous and local knowledge</i> as a source of transformative ways of knowing. The <i>poor availability and lack of regulation of sustainable technologies</i> , in association with <i>ineffective coordination of knowledge and innovation systems</i> act as barriers that challenge transformative change. These barriers can produce a lack of trust in evidence, including scientific evidence, for policy making.

Annex 4.3. Case Studies

4.3.1. Ocean: Fisheries case study

The United Nations Convention on Law of the Seas of 1982 and the Fish Stocks Agreement of 1995 paved the way for countries to take responsibilities in managing marine capture fisheries sustainably (Nakamura, 2023). However, after more than 40 years since the adoption of the first convention, the level of fish stocks that are sustainably exploited in Exclusive Economic Zones - namely in the Global South - continue to decline in the past decade (FAO, 2022b). Ocean governance is fragmented across various temporal and geographic scales (Erinosho et al., 2022) and inadequate and ineffective to address interlinked socio-ecological and (geo)political issues (Blythe et al., 2021; Spalding & Ycaza, 2020; Tokunaga et al., 2023). This is leading to increasing marine biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019), eroding the livelihoods of more than three billion of people who rely on seafood and fisheries including Indigenous Peoples and local communities (FAO et al., 2023) and undermining transformative change (Blythe et al., 2021). Production, commercialization and consumption patterns from intensive and extensive aquaculture and industrial commercial fisheries, often heavily subsidized, are embedded in the global food systems to meet increasing food demand of developed countries (Nash et al., 2022; Sumaila et al., 2019). While the negative impacts of these patterns on the marine biodiversity, earth's climate and well-being of coastal communities continue to exacerbate worldwide and especially in developing countries (M. Clark et al., 2022; Duong, 2018; Gephart et al., 2021).

Overfishing and the commodification of marine resources epitomize relations of domination that emerged in colonial eras, where the accumulation of resources and appropriation of the ocean are promoted and driven by a small number of multinational companies (Campling et al., 2012; B. Clark et al., 2018; Longo & Clausen, 2011; Mansfield, 2011). This historical dominant relation led to the increased exploitation of marine resources in several parts of the world such as West Africa, where extensive fishing by foreign fishing companies has led to strong decline in fish biomass and limited social and economic benefits (Alder & Sumaila, 2004; Okafor-Yarwood & Belhabib, 2020). The situation is often exacerbated by inadequate governance and corruption which prevent effective monitoring, control, and surveillance and enable widespread illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (Belhabib & Le Billon, 2020; Standing, 2015). Some oceanic regions including the Indian and Atlantic oceans are facing overfishing of highly traded species such as yellowfin tuna, round sardinella or European anchovy, often extracted for export by distant water fishing fleets and some coastal countries (IOTC, 2022; Palomares et al., 2020; Skerritt et al., 2023). In the Indian Ocean, tuna species such as yellowfin, bigeye or Spanish mackerel continue to be overfished due to exploitation by industrial fleets using high financial, technological and natural capital since the 1950s (Campling, 2012; Campling & Colás, 2021; Heidrich, Meeuwig, & Zeller, 2023; IOTC, 2022, 2016). To this is added the recent increase of catch in some artisanal fisheries and the industrialization of fisheries in the name of developing blue economies (Andriamahefazafy et al., 2020; Heidrich et al., 2023; IOTC, 2016, 2022). There is overwhelming evidence worldwide that current access to resources, as well as ocean benefits and harms, is characterized by a high concentration of the capital shared between a few fishing and aquaculture companies. Focusing on fisheries as a key sectoral example, between 2004 and 2014, 25 countries were responsible for roughly 82 per cent of global catches, and 10 companies control 11 to 16 per cent of global catches (Österblom et al., 2015).

Fishing access arrangements such as fisheries partnership agreements, vessel licencing or flagging allow powerful and rich countries to access fishing resources within coastal States'

Exclusive Economic Zones, mostly of developing ones (FAO, 2022a). These arrangements are a manifestation of power imbalance and inequalities, with fishing countries using their economic and geopolitical power to access resources at unfair prices and showing limited accountability on their impacts on marine resources (Campling et al., 2024; Gegout, 2016; Hammarlund & Andersson, 2019; Le Manach et al., 2021; Nichols et al., 2015). In West and East African regions, host coastal countries are caught in a challenging situation where they have limited means to monitor the depletion of resources caused by these arrangements but also rely on the revenues they generate for the national budget (Andriamahefazafy, 2023a; Le Manach et al., 2013; Okafor-Yarwood & Belhabib, 2020).

Measures adopted by Regional Fisheries Management Organizations that are tasked manage highly migratory transboundary species are still insufficient, and full cooperation to the extent necessary to ensure cross-sectoral cooperation is challenging (Haas et al., 2020; Heidrich et al., 2022). Even in the Western and Central Pacific tuna fisheries, which are regarded as relatively well-managed, conservation burdens are not shared equally and the arrangements fail to provide transparency in who is benefiting from efforts to conserve resources (Azmi & Hanich, 2021; Hanich et al., 2015). The situation in marine fisheries is similar to inland fisheries including for transboundary stocks (Friend et al., 2023; Midway et al., 2016). An institutional fit problem remains in adopting integrated and coherent conservation and management measures within ecologically meaningful boundaries (or ecosystem-based units/ functional units). Their sector-focused approach to management still poses an obstacle to managing these species. Species like sharks, for example, have seen drastic global decline despite measures adopted within regional fisheries management organizations or the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (Cronin et al., 2023; Pacoureau et al., 2021; Worm et al., 2024).

Further, there is an expansion of market-based approaches such as individual transferable quotas during the last three decades. The premise of such management approaches is based on the view that treat nature as economic assets. While studies have shown some benefits towards biological sustainability and climate resilience mostly in developed countries (Costello et al., 2008; Gaines et al., 2018), such approaches have also shown to have created adverse social outcomes and exacerbate existing inequities (Sumaila, 2010; Young et al., 2018). As seen in the case of Icelandic fisheries, which has expanded the use of individual transferable quotas since the 1970s, small-scale fishers and marginalized populations are often not able to fully benefit from such management or are negatively impacted via lost access to resources and livelihoods (Allison et al., 2012; Young et al., 2018).

A set of activities in fisheries that has a recognized detrimental impact on marine biodiversity is illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, affecting not only fish stocks but also marine ecosystems and species, the quality of the stock assessments and the capacity of States to obtain economic benefits from taxes (FAO, 2020; Gjerde et al., 2013). To address illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing, various technological advances for monitoring, control and surveillance are available: from devices such as drones, to monitoring systems such as automatic identification or vessel monitoring systems or data and information platforms such as Global Fishing Watch (Klawikowska et al., 2022; Toonen & Bush, 2020). While access and transfer of these technologies can help address illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (ibid), they also present challenges to transformative change. These include the unequal capacity to access, mobilize resources and use these monitoring, control and surveillance technologies (Cremers et al., 2020; Michelin et al., 2018). Data platforms can also invisibilise political and economic dynamics that are at the root causes of illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and offer a limited role to stakeholders such as fishers in the

implementation of these technologies, often developed and driven by a limited set of private actors (Drakopoulos et al., 2023; Toonen & Bush, 2020).

Despite long-standing research on the harmful effects of fisheries subsidies and the robust evidence of the large potential biodiversity-climate-society co-benefits of their removal (Skerritt et al., 2020; Skerritt & Sumaila, 2021), examples of transformative ocean governance across scales (international, national and local) have rarely been explicitly integrated within a biodiversity-climate-society nexus frame. Reframing subsidies is essential as they are a key driver of overfishing which is a major threat to ocean biodiversity, they also exacerbate carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from fishing sectors by incentivizing over-capacity and putting coastal livelihoods and food security at risk (Villasante et al., 2022). This would bring more active consideration of ocean-based solutions in policy discussions at the international and national levels. At the same time, ensuring social equity would require attention to not any vulnerable fishers that depend on subsidies not being harmed by their removal (Pascual et al., 2022), but also involves a paradigmatic and narrative shift. The way that governments and corporate actors think and talk about the role of the blue economy matters because norms and narratives fundamentally change how policies are eventually formulated, practices and development models. A second shift is that social sustainability and equity must move from the periphery to the centre of blue economy policy deliberations and documents. Discussions of how the blue economy can increase benefits to, and not harm, local coastal communities should pervade global, regional and national ocean policy meetings and governance processes. Inclusion, funding and foregrounding of representatives from coastal communities', small-scale fisheries' and Indigenous Peoples' organizations will enable them to speak on their own behalf about their visions and desired benefits (Bennett et al., 2022; Schutter et al., 2024).

Conventional fishery management approach focused on species of commercial value falls short of addressing bycatch and gear conflicts with protected species or species of no commercial value and neglects the impacts on the broader ecosystem through trophic interactions (Lewison et al., 2004; Pikitch et al., 2004). Ecosystem approaches can overcome challenges associated with single-species management and incorporate broad ecosystem interactions (e.g., food webs) and ecological processes that are essential for maintaining sustainability of the entire ecosystem and preserving biodiversity (Pikitch et al., 2004). Multiple countries and entities (e.g., Australia, International Council for the Exploration of the Sea) are working to develop methods and strategies to design, implement and evaluate ecosystem approaches to fisheries management and some countries have started (Fulton et al., 2014; Link et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2007). Yet, conventional management continues to focus solely on commercially important species.

One additional approach proposed that has a potential to overcome institutional fit challenge along with lack of consideration for non-target species and ecosystem interactions is Regional Seas Program, introduced by the United Nations Environment Programme. The programme is intended to support a more holistic ocean governance using area-based management tools, including marine protected areas (Erinosho et al., 2022). Integrative ocean governance can, therefore, be achieved through Regional Seas Programme and regional fisheries management organizations framework (Erinosho et al., 2022). To overcome the challenge of fragmented ocean governance that span across sectors and geographical boundaries and to deliver good outcomes at all scales, particularly in developing countries, strengthening of integrated partnerships between fisheries and environment sectors is required (Friedman et al., 2018).

Table SM.4.3. Supplementary material to support Box C Fisheries of Figure 4.4.

Presented barrier	Supportive literature	Where it links with chapter 4
Challenge 1 barrier: measure, simplify and manage	(Lewison et al., 2004; Pikitch et al., 2004)	Section 4.2.1
Challenge 1 barrier: justifying resource concentration	(Andriamahefazafy et al., 2020; Campling et al., 2012; Gegout, 2016; Heidrich, Meeuwig, Juan-Jordá, et al., 2023; Le Manach et al., 2021)	Section 4.2.1
Challenge 2 barrier: wealth and power shapes policy	(Campling et al., 2024; Hanich et al., 2015; Le Manach et al., 2013; Nichols et al., 2015; Okafor-Yarwood & Belhabib, 2020)	Section 4.2.2
Challenge 2: shareholder profit overrides public interests	(Le Manach et al., 2013; Sumaila et al., 2019)	Section 4.2.2
Challenge 3 barrier: rigid political-administrative boundaries	(Carr, 2004; Hanich et al., 2015; IOTC, 2022; Palacios-Abrantes et al., 2022; Plourde & Yeung, 1989; Tokunaga et al., 2023)	Section 4.2.3
Challenge 3 barrier: Uncoordinated institutions	(Erinosho et al., 2022; IOTC, 2022; Nichols et al., 2015; Plourde & Yeung, 1989)	Section 4.2.3
Challenge 3 barrier: social and ecological cycle mismatches	(Lewison et al., 2004; Pikitch et al., 2004)	Section 4.2.3
Challenge 3 barrier: understanding and measuring problems of fit	(Andriamahefazafy, 2023b; Erinosho et al., 2022; Lewison et al., 2004; Pikitch et al., 2004; White & Costello, 2011)	Section 4.2.3
Challenge 4 barrier: Telecoupling	(M. Clark et al., 2022; Duong, 2018; Gephart et al., 2021; Nash et al., 2022; Sumaila et al., 2019)	Section 4.2.4
Challenge 5 barrier: Inappropriate knowledge transfer and access to sustainable innovations	(Drakopoulos et al., 2023; Ewell et al., 2020; Okafor-Yarwood & Belhabib, 2020; Toonen & Bush, 2020)	Section 4.2.5

4.3.2. Land: Subsidies

Harmful subsidies are a persistent and critical driver of continuing biodiversity loss, but attempts to reform and eliminate perverse subsidies have widely failed (Bulte et al., 2007; IPBES, 2019). The Convention for Biological Diversity defines harmful subsidies as “government action that confers an advantage to consumers or producers [...] but in doing so, discriminates against sound environmental practices” (Joffe & Shepherd, 2020). Harmful subsidies include on-budget subsidies (including direct monetary transfers and loans to extractive industries), off-budget subsidies (such as tax breaks) and implicit subsidies (such as

non-internalized external costs and infrastructure/planning choices which ease extractive industry). In 2010, 193 governments agreed to identify, eliminate and reform subsidies leading to biodiversity loss (Aichi Target 3). As of 2018, only 19 countries had made progress and little has been made since then (Barbier, 2022; Dempsey et al., 2020; Perez, 2022). Through the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework governments re-committed to reform harmful subsidies by 2030. What stands in the way of subsidies reform? Why are subsidies harmful to biodiversity so challenging to reform or eliminate?

Subsidy lock-in literature holds that subsidies are often buried in tax codes and legal structures which involve administrative capacity and political will to identify and amend (Rentschler & Bazilian, 2017). There remains a widespread lack of awareness among policymakers about the ecological impacts of long-term subsidies to core national industries, especially considering the diverse forms that these subsidies take — from tax loopholes to long-term concessional loan agreements for extractive infrastructure (Cottrell, 2022; OECD, 2015). Many nations cannot or choose not to invest financial and administrative resources into the delicate process of subsidy reform.

Further, subsidies towards extractive industries such as intensive agriculture and fossil fuel production often lower costs for domestic consumers (Guillaume et al., 2011; Skovgaard & Van Asselt, 2019). Eliminating them risks price increases in fuel and food, which harm the most socioeconomically vulnerable (Rentschler & Bazilian, 2017). Hasty subsidy reform can also provoke political unrest, making it an unattractive position for politicians (McCulloch, 2023). Externally motivated subsidy reform can also enforce austerity, which can exacerbate domestic and international inequality (Dempsey et al., 2020; Tamale, 2021). Still, these barriers are surmountable — redirecting harmful and inefficient public finance flows towards public good spending can positively impact both biodiversity and equity. Precedents recommend identifying and communicating which ecologically-degrading subsidies primarily benefit the wealthy, then gradually phasing them out (McCulloch, 2023).

Harmful subsidies also persist due to “powerful vested interests in favour of the maintenance of existing subsidy schemes” (Cottrell, 2022). These interests, which often come in the form of extractive industries, exert political power to maintain the subsidies that contribute to their profits, despite noted environmental harms (Dempsey et al., 2020; Guerriero et al., 2020; McCulloch, 2023; Turnhout et al., 2021). These subsidies not only motivate ecological damaging economies, but also they often privilege the already-privileged with greater concentrations of land and wealth (Bulte et al., 2007; Heyl et al., 2021; Pe’er et al., 2020; Stubenrauch et al., 2022). This has been documented regarding agricultural subsidies in the European Union and Brazil, as well as how inequitable distribution of global fishery subsidies motivate unsustainable overfishing by high-income countries (Skerritt et al., 2023). In this context, practices such as industry lobbying and the inequitable concentration of land and power both within and between nations represent obstacles to achieving Aichi Target 3 and to the process of transformative change (Green & Healy, 2022; IPBES, 2019).

Many governments, especially those with primary product export-based economies, also struggle to make subsidies for conservation competitive with globalized market incentives to cultivate biodiversity-detracting cash crops (Chibwana et al., 2013; Manushevich & Beier, 2016; Sloan, 2016). For example, Chile’s National Forest Law has been unsuccessful at conserving native forests because high rents for non-native forest plantations make biodiversity-detracting afforestation more profitable for landowners (Manushevich & Beier, 2016). Loopholes in the National Forest Law align closely with policy proposals put forward by forestry industry lobbyists, who argue that land-owners have the right to cater to the international market to garner the most value from their property (Manushevich & Beier,

2016). Consequently, harmful subsidy lock-in is also a symptom of international capital mobility and political influence to entrench export-oriented natural resource markets

Barriers to Subsidy Reform

Figure SM.4.1. Barriers to subsidy phase and reform.

4.3.3. River ecosystems: The problems of fit

These problems of fit can manifest in various ways. Common examples relate to institutional factors mismatching with social-ecological dynamics. In the Mekong River basin, for instance, broader institutional arrangements such as transboundary agreements fail to account for more nuanced, finer-scale social-ecological dynamics such as local subsistence fisheries as well as rice cultivation (Sneddon & Fox, 2006). This misfit is a key challenge for transformative change as the livelihood conditions of millions of people are affected by these broader governance arrangements that are disconnected from these local and vital social-ecological processes. In another example from the Yahara agricultural watershed in Wisconsin, United States of America, important mismatches were found between water policies and water-related ecosystem services (Qiu et al., 2017). In total, 30 policies and four key services (freshwater supply, groundwater and surface water quality and flood regulation) were analyzed and spatial misfits were identified between water policy implementation and the relevant water quality areas. Policy instruments in this case were not effectively targeting the main causes of water quality problems, particularly in agriculture-dominated regions, which has important consequences for the sustainability of key water resources in the region. Another example of problems of fit between jurisdictional and biophysical systems are represented in Exclusive Economic Zones. As institutional arrangements originally intended to improve marine resource management, Exclusive Economic Zones have in many cases been unsuccessful given the mismatch between the jurisdictional scope of the zone and the marine species' ecological dynamics that transcend these zones (Young, 2008).

One example of a social misfit can be seen in the overall expressed environmental concern of the Costa Rican population and the actions taken to remediate environmental problems. In a national-level survey conducted in 2017 (Lentini, 2017; Programa Estado de La Nación, 2017), almost 70 per cent of respondents rank environmental issues as equally or more important than matters such as poverty reduction, improving health and education systems and reducing corruption and social inequality. This attitude reflects, in part, broader political and institutional efforts undertaken since the 1980s that have promoted sustainability within Costa Rican civil society. Such efforts have included, for instance, consolidating a robust environmental policy framework including payment for ecosystem services, as well as establishing a representative network of conservation areas. Despite this broader institutional culture, however, about 73 per cent of respondents expressed that actions at the agency level have been insufficient; that is, people do not do enough to remediate environmental problems, evidencing a mismatch between thinking and action in the general population regarding environmental issues. This is relevant for transformative change as solving this misfit can prompt individual-level actions that, due to their cumulative nature, can lead to large-scale sustainability transformations.

4.3.4. Challenges of the intellectual property rights systems

The intellectual property rights systems, such as patents, trademarks and copyrights, play a complex role, both positive and negative roles, in the context of facilitating or hindering transformative change (Eppinger et al., 2021). The impact of intellectual property rights on innovation is influenced by the level of absorptive capacity in a country, which refers to the ability to identify, analyze and utilize new technologies (Hammami, 2021). The literature also reports different effects depending on the methodological characteristics of each study (Neves et al., 2021). On one hand, intellectual property rights can foster and support creativity, sustainable innovation, diffusion and social and economic development in society by

protecting the rights of inventors and creators and incentivizing them to invest time and resources into research and development (Chen & Puttitanun, 2005; Duch-Brown & Costa-Campi, 2015; Eppinger et al., 2021; Olubiyi et al., 2022; Schiederig et al., 2012; Ziedonis, 2008). Abolishing intellectual property rights can reduce innovation incentives (Griffith & Van Reenen, 2023). However, despite the positive impacts of intellectual property rights systems on innovations and economic development in developing countries (Chen & Puttitanun, 2005; Forero-Pineda, 2006), these effects are weaker in developing countries than developed countries (Chen & Puttitanun, 2005; Hammami, 2021; Neves et al., 2021; Olubiyi et al., 2022). Many obstacles have prevented developing countries from benefiting from the intellectual property rights that could help them grow. These countries have faced various difficulties in protecting intellectual property rights, such as the inadequacy of laws for intellectual property right protection in these countries and other factors that confront the protection and exploitation of intellectual property rights in making a significant contribution to their development, including education, the internet, technology, enforcement, financial empowerment, awareness and lack of a general intellectual property culture (Le et al., 2023; Olubiyi et al., 2022).

On the other hand, intellectual property rights systems can pose significant challenges to transformative change by creating barriers and delaying innovation diffusion to access and use of knowledge and technology by others (Eppinger et al., 2021). Intellectual property rights, particularly patents, can also create monopolies or oligopolies that stifle competition and innovation in certain markets or sectors (Gilbert, 2020; Griffith & Van Reenen, 2023). Intellectual property rights can also generate conflicts and disputes among different stakeholders over the ownership, scope, validity or enforcement of the protected rights. Intellectual property rights can create inequalities within and among countries in terms of their capacities and opportunities to participate in and benefit from the innovation process (Olubiyi et al., 2022; Séjourné, 2020). Stronger international intellectual property rights protection can limit the international cooperation and access to information for scientific communities in developing countries, as they have to work harder to achieve normal science results (Forero-Pineda, 2006). Intellectual property rights can make innovation more costly, difficult and reduce the chances of inventing in developing countries (Hammami, 2021).

Literature suggests conducting in-depth research and taking a comprehensive perspective to enhance and protect intellectual property rights to overcome the multifaceted challenges affecting intellectual property rights, particularly towards sustainability and the circular economy (Eppinger et al., 2021; Olubiyi et al., 2022). The intellectual property rights systems are also expected to structurally support organizations towards transformative change by removing institutional difficulties for sustainable innovation diffusion. Intellectual property rights are not neutral instruments that automatically lead to transformative change. They are contingent on the legal, institutional, economic, social and cultural contexts in which they operate. The impact of intellectual property rights on transformative change depends on how they are designed, implemented, interpreted and enforced by various actors at different levels. Finding the optimal balance between protecting the rights of creators and inventors and promoting the public interest and social welfare, remains a major challenge for policymakers, lawmakers, researchers, businesses and civil society.

4.3.5. Case studies illustrating ways to overcome the challenges

From the transformative change case study database¹¹, after careful reading and screening the following three case studies that illustrate ways of overcoming the challenges led by social movements, by communities and by government were identified.

Social movement

The Chipko movement was a non-violent uprising that originated in Chamoli, Uttar Pradesh (now Uttarakhand), India, in 1973 (Shiva & Bandyopadhyay, 1986; The Indian Express, 2018). Villagers, especially women, became active stewards of the forests that they were dependent upon. They stood up against commercial timber contractors and hugged the trees to prevent them from being felled. The movement influenced several similar uprisings across the country wherein forest fringe-dwellers stood up against forest destruction. It finally led to the implementation of the Forest Conservation Act of 1980 (Mundoli, 2024). The movement further stands out as an eco-feminist movement as women were instrumental in this endeavour.

Pathway involved in overcoming challenges towards a sustainable world: Active disruption

Community-led initiative

The Len Ko Winkul Mapu is a recent initiative that aims to halt biodiversity degradation in Patagonia with potentially huge long-term benefits for biodiversity and people. Started by the Lof Cayun Panicheo, a trans-Andean Mapuche community that has maintained a deep relationship with land through its ancestral occupation, the project has elaborated a conservation plan to strengthen its resistance to several industrial projects, including hydroelectric dams and salmon farming alongside unsustainable tourism, land privatization, and land grabbing (Lof Cayun Panicheo, 2020).

Pathway involved in overcoming challenges towards a sustainable world: Phasing out industries that are uncondusive to biodiversity safeguarding.

Government initiative

Changing policies and governance structures were among the principal drivers underlying deceleration in deforestation in Brazil since 2004 (Nepstad et al., 2014). For example, a territorial performance approach to deforestation, implemented at the county level instead of the individual farm, was effective in this regard. The Critical Counties program, launched through a collaboration between the Environment Ministry and the Central Bank, restricted access to agricultural credit to farms and ranches in counties with the highest rates of deforestation.

Pathways involved in overcoming challenges towards a sustainable world: active disruption, empowering new structures, collaboration between agencies.

4.3.6. Challenges identified and represented in the case study database

Table SM.4.4. Identifying challenges in the case study database

Total number of case studies	391
Total number of challenges identified across all case studies	859 (294 case studies mentioned more than one challenge)

¹¹ Case studies database with transformative potential and pitfalls (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260233>)

Number of case studies that had ‘Other’ as a response. Note: Overall 23 case studies included ‘Other’ as a response. Based on the explanation provided for ‘Other’ in the succeeding column of the database, 16 responses could be mapped to one or more of the five overarching challenges	7
Number of case studies that had ‘NA’ as a response	1
Percentage of responses (N=859) that mentioned:	
Challenge 1	19.32
Challenge 2	22.24
Challenge 3	19.44
Challenge 4	23.52
Challenge 5	14.55

Method

The case study database was used for this analysis. The typology of ‘challenges’ provided in the database questionnaire was the one included in the first order draft of chapter 4. Those responses were mapped onto the typology of ‘overarching challenges’ finalized by chapter 4 in the further revised draft. For example, ‘Affects and emotions and how they interact with cognitive views have been neglected in relation to social and environmental transformative change processes’, ‘Socio-psychological lock-ins across individuals and/or collectives/communities’ and ‘Views of biodiversity as separate from humans and as such, to be controlled, managed and exploited’ were coded as challenge 1. In certain instances, if respondents chose ‘Other’ as an option, based on additional comments that they provided, the assessment experts categorized those as per the typology included in the further revised draft of chapter 4. For example, “Violation of Indigenous Peoples and vulnerable groups rights” was coded as challenge 1. When such coding was not possible, the response was considered as ‘Other’ (table SM.4.4).

Table SM.4.5. Mapping of challenges mentioned in the database onto the typology provided by chapter 4

Challenge identified in database	Comments provided	Overarching challenge
Affects and emotions and how they interact with cognitive views have been neglected in relation to social and environmental transformative change processes		Challenge 1
Avoid past overexploitation of the fishery and atomization of the fisheries sector		Challenge 4
Concentration of wealth		Challenge 2
Concentrations of power associated with current dominant economic systems (capitalism)		Challenge 2
Concentrations of wealth		Challenge 2
Conforming actions that create a hold on habits and institutions over social life		Challenge 4
Current patterns in human movement and migration		Challenge 4

Financial insecurity		Challenge 2
Fortress approaches to conservation		Challenge 1
Inadequate policies and institutions and their misalignment to redirect capital to biodiversity actions		Challenge 3
Inadequate policies and institutions and their misalignment to redirect capital to biodiversity actions. Unsustainable production and consumption patterns		Challenge 3
Lack of collective arena to imagine and plan for a common, transformed future		Challenge 5
Lack of coordination between knowledge and innovation stakeholders, including limited coordination and cooperation of researchers across disciplines		Challenge 5
Lack of data collection, organizational structures and direct marketing opportunities		Challenge 3, 5
Local community coordination		Challenge 1
Marginalization of women from the management of shell fishing resources		Challenge 1
Market and risk-based approaches that make it difficult to progress biodiversity conservation and restoration measures or agenda		Challenge 3
Market and risk-based approaches that make it difficult to progress biodiversity conservation and restoration measures or agendas		Challenge 3
Market and risk-based approaches that make it difficult to progress biodiversity conservation and restoration measures or agendas.		Challenge 3
Misalignment between institutional arrangements and broader cultures		Challenge 3
Misalignments among local sectors that deal with urban planning and environmental protection		Challenge 3
Neoliberal (re)structuring of state policies, including liberalization and austerity		Challenge 3
Other	Impacts of climate change	Other
Other	Marginalization of small-scale fisheries in educational systems	Challenge 1
Other	Faced with demographic pressure and an ever-increasing number of cars, Curitiba is stepping up its efforts to retain its image as the Brazilian leader in terms of sustainable cities and the fight against climate change.	Challenge 4
Other	Population growth	Challenge 4
Other	Violation of Indigenous Peoples rights and customs	Challenge 1
Other	Violation of Indigenous Peoples and vulnerable groups rights	Challenge 1

Other	Invisibilization of women in the EU fisheries sector	Challenge 1
Other	Biotechnology	Challenge 5
Other	Poor child nutrition and poor/lack of education are one of the most important challenges for human development.	Other
Other	Increasing poverty in Spain	Challenge 2
Other	Preserving street art	Other
Other	Polio	Other
Other	Collaboration between countries that have histories of conflict	Other
Other		Other
Other	Lack/low recognition of Sámi peoples' rights	Challenge 1
Other	Women invisibilization	Challenge 1
Other	Public-private relationship for sustainability	Challenge 5
Other	Equality access to freshwater in rural areas	Challenge 2
Other	Challenges were not overcome yet, Russian aggression continues, threats remain	Other
Overexploitation of fishery resources and the Prestige oil spill		Challenge 4
Policy-related challenges		Challenge 3
Poverty reduction		Challenge 2
Power inequalities and associated dominant values of materialism		Challenge 2
Socio-psychological lock-ins across individuals and/or collectives/communities		Challenge 1
Socio-psychological lock-ins across individuals and/or collectives/communities	this initiative has been able to demonstrate that Indigenous management of natural areas is possible, contradicting the state's approach (an approach that most of the time does not respect Indigenous land rights).	Challenge 1
Spatial, temporal and functional misfits between jurisdictional and biophysical boundaries that create blind spots		Challenge 3
Technological innovations/Lack of or limited access to clean technologies		Challenge 5
The state has a "glass ceiling" for how far it will support environmental protection measures		Challenge 3

Unsustainable production and consumption patterns		Challenge 4
Unsustainable production and consumption patterns	Lock-in of conventional, harmful agricultural practices	Challenge 4
Urbanization		Challenge 4
Values		Challenge 1
Views of biodiversity as separate from humans and as such, to be controlled, managed and exploited		Challenge 1
Views of biodiversity as separate from humans and as such, to be controlled, managed and exploited	The key challenge was to solve how to develop sustainable and health cities for the population.	Challenge 1, Challenge 4

If after mapping, any case study was found to include multiple challenges that could be mapped onto a single overarching challenge as per the further revised draft, it was counted only once. For example, Response 89 (R89) mentioned challenge 2 thrice and challenge 4 twice. For the final analysis, the assessment authors counted each of these once (**Table SM4.5**).

Table SM4.6. Example showing that a case study may mention a single overarching challenge multiple times.

If case studies mention a single overarching challenge multiple times, the said challenge is counted only once for the purpose of this exercise.

R89	Concentrations of power associated with current dominant economic systems (capitalism)	Challenge 2
R89	Current patterns in human movement and migration	Challenge 4
R89	Financial insecurity	Challenge 2
R89	Neoliberal (re)structuring of state policies, including liberalization and austerity	Challenge 3
R89	Power inequalities and associated dominant values of materialism	Challenge 2
R89	Unsustainable production and consumption patterns	Challenge 4

The number of times that each overarching challenge (1 to 5) was mentioned was then expressed as a percentage of the total number of challenges mentioned (N = 859).

4.3.7. Data used to produce figure 4.7 and 4.8

The National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts 2023 Public Data Package Excel file was downloaded on the 22nd of February, 2024, from the Global Footprint Network website (Global Footprint Network et al., 2023). To create the bar graphs with the different income classes, the Country Results (2019) sheet was used, as it contains real data and the 2022 contains estimates for the latest years. The data from the columns 'Total Ecological Footprint (Production)', 'Total Ecological Footprint (Consumption)' and 'Total Biocapacity' was used, which is in global hectares per person. The total refers to the different types of production, consumption and capacity, which are added together (and not to the consumption of all people from an income class taken together).

The maps were also created with the data from the Country Results (2019) data, with data from the same columns: columns 'Total Ecological Footprint (Production)', 'Total Ecological

Footprint (Consumption)' and 'Total Biocapacity'. Because of the variation in production, consumption and biocapacity between the regions provided, these regions were used for the maps and not the IPBES regions (for which North, Central and Caribbean and South America would have been taken together, as well as the European Unions countries and other European countries).

The line diagrams for the various income classes through time were based on the data at the country level from the Global Footprint Network website (Global Footprint Network et al., 2023) for which the Ecological Footprint vs Biocapacity (gha per person) was downloaded on the 21st of May 2024. Population sizes for each country were downloaded from the World Bank (*World Bank Open Data*, n.d.), also on the 21st of May 2024. The income classes were taken from the National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts 2023 dataset, from the Country Results (2019) sheet. The biocapacity and ecological footprint for each country was multiplied with the population size of that country, and the results for all countries were added together, and divided by the total number of people in an income class per year. There are a few countries that changed dramatically during 1960 and 2022, such as Czechoslovakia that was split into the Czech Republic and Slovakia in 1992. In such cases, only the most recent countries were used, as the information on the income classes is not available through time, but only at the 2019 level. Therefore, the ecological footprint and biocapacity of Czechoslovakia was not included, but since 1992, the data for the Czech Republic and Slovakia was.

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Annex 4.4. Additional information on challenges

4.4.1 Habits and transformative change

Habits form and are learned in regard to certain contexts. Habits create a fit between humans needs and the restrictions and opportunities of the social and environmental conditions. In the case studies examples this includes the seemingly “unlimited appropriation of resources, space, territories, labour and sinks elsewhere” resulting in what has been called an “imperial mode of living” (Brand & Wissen, 2018). Because habits per definition conform to a certain situation, they are for this reason described as dragons of inaction. A significant barrier to transformative change lies in the hold that habits and institutions have over social life and our inter-actions with nature (Gunderson, 2023). Actions that conform, reinforce and transmit existing social conditions to following generations are common because human action is inherently habitual.

In contrast, transformative change includes discontinuing actions which threaten biodiversity and ecosystems and allowing for transformative actions to take hold that can allow for environmentally sustainable societies. The hold of habits and institutions over social life is never total. Otherwise, people would not have been able to change ourselves and our societies. Apart from their ingrained capacity to learn and sensitivity to other humans, it is also part of human nature to be able to perceive and sense the self. In so doing, people can think and experience themselves as individuals with urges, desires, thoughts, ideas, wishes, etc., apart from the group to which they belong. This experience produces individual thoughts and ideas against prevailing institutions, sometimes called the “tendency for realization” (Davies, 2012). Transformative ideas and actions spring from this tendency and have the potential to break habits (Axon, 2017) and as such transform society. But only on the condition that new ideas and actions are copied by others and, in turn, form habits and institutions.

So far habits remain underexplored in relation to transformative change and sustainability (Linder et al., 2022). They are often only used to denote a certain type of routine and automatic behaviour (Longoria et al., 2021) and not understood as a fundamental motivation and explanation for human social practices (Lizardo, 2021). So, when considering the role of habits in relation to the origin and development of processes of transformative change, the lessons drawn include:

- Habits can easily withstand new information and knowledge. To break them down involves that people beside knowledge feel the consequences of their behaviour. With this knowledge in mind, it becomes imperative to ensure that people feel the consequences of their actions
- Habits can be changed when people go through change (migration, new family, etc.). When people experience changes, they are more open to consider alternative modes of behaviour and living. This is called the “Habit discontinuity hypothesis”.
- Maximize openness to new ideas and actions.
- The stability and predictability of context is the prime condition for the persistence of habits. Attention needs to be given to the manipulation of context (external triggers) by creating incentives. But attention also needs to be paid to the internalization of values so that habits are formed.

To change unsustainable habits people’s ingrained capacity to learn and sensitivity to other humans is fundamental, but also to be able to perceive and sense the self. In so doing, people

can think and experience themselves as individuals with urges, desires, thoughts, ideas, wishes, etc., apart from the group to which they belong. This experience produces individual thoughts and ideas that allow people to consider themselves, to question and reflect about their motivations and behaviour and thus to also change themselves. For instance, a global survey reported that two in three people are prepared to reduce consumption by half to avoid environmental damage and climate change (GLOBESCAN, 2022; see also Vollebregt et al., 2024). The experience of self thus enables people to change against prevailing values, norms and institutions (Davies, 2012). Transformative ideas and actions spring from this tendency and have the potential to break habits (Axon, 2017) and, as such, transform society.

4.4.2. Habits in relation to transformative change

Perhaps the most significant barrier to transformative change lies in the hold that habits and institutions have over social life (Gunderson, 2023). How can the gap between the concern for unsustainable outcomes (e.g., biodiversity loss) of human behaviour and the persistence of this type of behaviour be explained? A number of scholars suggest that perhaps cognition, knowledge and conscious deliberation are overrated as motivators, or drivers, of action (Haidt, 2013) and that something else has a much stronger grip over views and actions (Grant, 2021). In search for an answer what this ‘something else’ can be social scientists propose instincts, desires, beliefs, emotions, or values. Yet, although these are admittedly non-rational motivations, they do not explain the gap that lies between valuing or desiring to protect nature and actions that go against it. Apparently, human action is not generated by motivations only (whether rational or irrational; conscious or subconscious).

The concept of habit can explain why and how actions can occur relatively independent from human motivations. Habits fall between instinct and reason (Camic, 1986; Carlisle, 2014; Darwin, 1871, 1872; Dewey, 1975; Duhigg, 2014; Grosz, 2013; Hodgson, 2006; James, 1890; Kilpinen, 2000). Reasoning is deliberative and conscious and something people do to make choices and reflect on their preferences. Instinct, in contrast, refers to actions that are performed automatically, without little or no conscious awareness. Habits involve both types of action but not in equal measure all the time. Much habitual behaviour occurs quasi-deliberate, automatically and routine-like, but was once a deliberate and conscious choice of action. Through habit formation conscious choice and actions become embodied and instinctive as “second nature” (Ravaisson, 2009; Ringmar, 2017) “ingrained patterns of thought, action and feeling that direct our lives in predictable ways” (Davies, 2012).

Habits thus refer not to a specific type of action but rather to settled dispositions; a tendency to act and think in a certain way; recurrent behaviour. They can be acquired by frequent repetition of the same act until it becomes almost or quite involuntary. They also can be learned from others (through, for instance, mimicking). Habits in the latter respect refer to settled practices, customs and customary ways or manners of action. People are taught habits of doing, thinking and feeling by members of the group in which they were born, such as their parents or other family or group members. Through group socialization people are able to meaningfully interact. As such habits provide meaning, coherence and security to social life and ultimately people’s survival and that of the social group to which they belong. In turn, habits of doing, thinking and feeling are consolidated and reproduced in social practices “bundles of attitudes and behaviours which in a society at a given time are considered as meaningful and culturally accepted” (Verplanken & Whitmarsh, 2021). These social practices in turn can institutionalize as ‘traditions’, ‘customs’, ‘norms’ etc. – through which habits are reproduced in new generations (Zijderveld, 2001). This process whereby habits constitute

social practices and institutions underpins human social behaviour and the coherence and continuation of human societies over time.

4.4.3. Habits and sustainability

In relation to sustainability problems habits are described as “dragons of inaction” (Gifford, 2011; Kelly & Barker, 2016; Linder et al., 2022; Marien et al., 2019) and as “*psychological barriers*” (Gifford et al., 2018). Indeed, there are many examples where habits are strong and make people do things that (they know) are not good for the environment. A number of studies have appeared that point out how a number of practices (eating and drinking; clothing; moving around) are deeply habitual, e.g., eating and drinking (Adriaanse et al., 2017; Eustachio Colombo et al., 2021; Kekeunou et al., 2021; Rees et al., 2018; Russell & Knoeri, 2019); clothing (Cano et al., 2019; Henninger, 2015; Hugo et al., 2022); moving around, (Fujii & Kitamura, 2003; Gärling & Axhausen, 2003; Peng et al., 2017; Ramos et al., 2020; Schwanen et al., 2012; Verplanken et al., 1997); waste handling (Whitmarsh et al., 2018).

4.4.4. Conformist practices

Actions that conform, reinforce, and transmit existing social conditions to following generations are common because human action is inherently habitual. The role of habits has been linked to social practices, including the values, norms, and institutions that people conform to, making them stable and hence difficult to change. The hold of habits and institutions on social life is never total because people importantly have the capacity to reflect consciously and deliberately upon their (changing) context and their own and other actions therein. Such reflection is triggered especially under conditions where (due to environmental changes) habitual practices no longer are able to fulfil aspirations and needs. Under these circumstances people can experience “doubt” (Peirce, 1982) or “uneasiness” (Veblen, 1994) which leads to reflection and creativity (Joas, 1996) through the possibility of re-constructing habitual ways of thinking, feeling, and doing (Dewey, 1975; Gross, 2009). It is emphasized that habitual ways of thinking, feeling and doing are reconstructed because they cannot be completely demolished or disintegrated because that would leave people in a moral and cultural void. As emphasized by Dewey: “If the habits are entirely resolved, or disintegrated, there is no efficient instrumentality by which the new aims may realize themselves. The person relapses into a moral pulp. [...] The expression of the old habit carries within itself the making over of the old habit” (Dewey, 1975; Mead, 1981).

4.4.5. Gene-editing technologies

The application of gene editing technologies is in its early stages, yet is growing at a rapid pace, making it difficult to foresee the future consequences of its use. Thus, this assessment is not intended to be a comprehensive review of its challenges, but rather to highlight the most important barriers to achieving a sustainable world, based on reviews and syntheses of the topic. Barriers that could arise in the application of gene editing technology may include ethical and social challenges, safety risks, inequalities in access and benefit distribution, as well as the need for strict regulations and decision making processes of equitable and inclusive decisions.

First, barriers due to the lack of proper safeguards include the need of risk assessments, efficacy and management for application fields such as food systems, human health and the environment (Agapito-Tenfen et al., 2018; D. R. Gordon et al., 2021; Pixley et al., 2022). The plethora of possible technologies, applications, mechanisms and contexts hinder a comprehensive evaluation of gene editing's risks and benefits, necessitating case-specific

analysis (Eckerstorfer et al., 2023; Friedrichs et al., 2019). Robust risk assessment approaches are needed in real scenarios (Eckerstorfer et al., 2023), especially in applications involving novel or complex traits (Eckerstorfer et al., 2023). The existing risk assessment framework was designed for classical genetic modification techniques and adapting it to new gene-editing methods poses challenges, including traceability and detection (Agapito-Tenfen et al., 2018). The robust assessment of risks and benefits require reliable data and independent scientific evidence for responsible use of emerging technologies (Corlett, 2017; Jordan et al., 2017; Kofler et al., 2018). Advantages of modified organisms for enhancement of water and soil exploitation could be compromised by potential issues such as increased irrigation and agrochemical usage, harmful impacts on soils and the yield of other crops, or broader consequences of extensive cultivation like disturbances in regional hydrology. Furthermore, the widespread cultivation of some gene edited crops has the potential to alter agricultural economies and landscapes, leading to potential societal, economic and cultural effects (Jordan et al., 2017). Secondly, weak or non-inclusive social engagement results in a lack of input from communities and stakeholders, resulting in a lack of dialogue to incorporate diverse points of view (Baltimore et al., 2015; I. Gordon et al., 2021). Challenges in using gene-editing techniques involve recognition that scientific debates cannot occur in isolation. Scepticism toward expertise necessitates building public trust in science and technical institutions (Braun & Meacham, 2019). To navigate complexities, society engagement is essential, with an emphasis on Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Hudson et al., 2019; Kofler et al., 2018; Kuzma & Grieger, 2020). Inclusive discussions, involving experts and public audiences, are needed for transparent decision-making, ensuring a future aligned with societal values (Jasanoff & Hurlbut, 2018). Lack of social engagement may lead to polarization and misinformation such as current examples of populist parties doubting expertise on issues from climate change to vaccination (Braun & Meacham, 2019).

Third, challenges for a transformative change using gene editing technologies involve the overlook of ethical considerations alongside religious principles and spiritual views. Special concerns revolve around animal welfare (de Graeff et al., 2019) and unintended heritable effects in humans that could affect future generations that had no say in the decision process (Carroll & Charo, 2015). Farm animals were edited to improve production efficiency, some of these genome modifications could result in secondary complications that are bad for animal welfare. The resurgence of eugenics ethical concerns.

Fourth, gene editing's regulatory gaps result in unclear policy guidance for the use of novel technologies (Monast, 2018; Pixley et al., 2022). Updated regulations need dynamic, case-by-case norms designed to address the rapid pace of innovation (Corlett, 2017; Kjeldaas et al., 2023) and consideration of regulating outcomes and in cases, regulating the technology itself. Regulatory frameworks vary internationally and locally, with incomplete mechanisms to address collateral effects (I. Gordon et al., 2021; Zarate et al., 2023). Appropriate standards for risk assessments, intellectual property and regulatory complexities remain issues (Carroll & Charo, 2015; Pixley et al., 2022). Internationally harmonized regimes would help to facilitate gene editing's legitimacy, especially in countries with less robust regulatory regimes (Zarate et al., 2023). Advanced gene-editing technologies pose a risk of benefiting wealthy players while disadvantaging smallholders and alternative agriculture systems (Pixley et al., 2022). As new technologies and their applications, evolve faster than regulatory processes, a good governance body is needed to address sustainably the rapid rise of innovations (I. Gordon et al., 2021; Hurlbut, 2019; Monast, 2018). It is seen as a first line of intervention, offering inclusive discussions, best practice guidelines and public tracking for gene-edited applications entering the market (Jordan et al., 2017; Kuzma & Grieger, 2020). It promotes open debates on ethical, ecological and legal aspects of gene editing where local communities,

technology companies and governmental and non-governmental organizations are equally involved (Eckerstorfer et al., 2023; Kuiken et al., 2021). The proposed coordinating body could be based on similar experiences such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and organized on established United Nations platforms (Kofler et al., 2018).

4.4.6. Clean technologies

Despite the substantial literature on the positive impact of clean technologies, there is some evidence of the potential positive and negative impacts of these technologies on biodiversity and conservation activities. For instance, some cases on terrestrial biomass energy, hydropower, marine-hydrokinetic energy, wind energy, solar energy and mining for renewable energy resources reflect the complexity between renewable energy technologies and biodiversity, particularly their negative impacts on fauna, though each renewable energy source has its unique conservation concerns and offers a distinctive set of opportunities for mitigation (Jager et al., 2021; Roddis, 2018; Sonter et al., 2020; Stumvoll, 2019). Similar positive effects or concerns may raise for other modern and emerging technologies, including precise or smart agriculture (application of blockchain, drones, the Internet of Things, Agriculture 4.0, Industry 4.0, etc), remote sensing and artificial intelligence genetic modification technology, nanotechnology and bioeconomy (Ammann, 2005; Breed et al., 2019; Carpenter, 2011; De Schutter, 2017; European Parliament, 2023; Freckleton et al., 2004; Garcia & Altieri, 2005; Jacobsen et al., 2013; Javaid et al., 2022; Maraveas, 2023; Masehela et al., 2020; Muzhinji & Ntuli, 2021; Reynolds, 2020; E. G. Sutherland et al., 2009; W. J. Sutherland et al., 2009; Watkinson et al., 2000). For instance, AI may have long-term effects of introducing new varieties or breeds on biodiversity and natural flora and fauna (European Parliament, 2023).

These issues highlight the need for more research on the potential environmental implications of these technologies and developing sustainable technologies that provide society with economic prosperity, food security, well-being and climate change adaptation and mitigation while protect future biodiversity. It is also necessary to share knowledge among modern or emerging technology experts, biodiversity experts, policy makers and resource managers.

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